

Natural Language Processing (NER) for Automated News Tagging and Categorization

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Abstract— The automated news analysis, Tagging and categorization solves various challenges to offer a comprehensive and effective news analysis experience. Using the Google Cloud Translate API, it effortlessly translates news descriptions to English, addressing the problem of multilingual content and guaranteeing cross-language accessibility for consumers. When it comes to recognizing parts of the news like Names or places the system is very accurate. It combines SpaCy NLP model with TextBlob for sentiment analysis, Notably the system uses cloud vision API for predicting the news category and accuracy. The system also does a job summarizing news articles in a way that's easy to understand. It uses Transformers models for this which produce summaries that are clear and informative. If there are any images in the news article the system can detect objects in them using DETR model. Using the objects detected All these solutions work together to improve efficiency and inclusiveness.

Keywords: SpaCy, TextBlob, Named Entity Recognition (NER), Google Cloud Vision API, Google NLP API, Google Translate, Transformers

I. INTRODUCTION

In the digital era of information overload, news analysis and Categorization has become paramount. This automated system can tackle the challenges in news analysis. Leveraging cutting-edge technologies such as NER using NLP, sentimental analysis, text summarization and image processing the system allows users to input news description in any language System overcome multilingual content challenges and improved entity recognition precision. The system offers clear, concise news summaries and efficient object detection in images. Additionally, the integration of Google Cloud Vision API enhances automated news categorization. The collective integration of these diverse solutions culminates in a highly efficient and inclusive news analysis and categorization system.

II. RELATED WORKS

A. "Generalized Named Entity Recognition Framework"
By Darshita Kumar, Shambhavi Pandey

The paper proposes replacing Computer Vision with Named Entity Recognition (NER) for data extraction from OCR-processed document images. It introduces a flexible NER framework and annotation tool, STAT, and discusses results based on different configurations.

B. An Efficient method for Aspect Based Sentiment

Analysis Using SpaCy and Vader by Akhilesh Kumar Singh, Ananya

This paper Focuses on Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis, transitioning from traditional Sentiment Analysis to better understand. It presents an NLP model trained on text/reviews and uses tools like Vader, TextBlob, and SpaCy for efficient sentiment and aspect mining.

C. A Replicable Comparison Study of NER Software: StanfordNLP, NLTK, OpenNLP, SpaCy, Gate by Xavier Schmitt, Sylvain Kubler

This paper aims to address the challenge of objectively evaluating Named Entity Recognition (NER) software in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP). The study compares five prominent NER software versions against two distinct corpora.

D. Mastering spaCy: An end-to-end practical guide to implementing NLP applications using the Python ecosystem.

Duygu Altınok Mastering Spacy paper gives an overview of how spaCy helps for building real world applications and also how to use popular frameworks TensorFlow Keras API together with spaCy.

III. APPROACH TO AUTOMATED NEWS TAGGING AND CATEGORIZATION

The system contains mainly two operations first of detecting the user language while creating the news converting them into English using google translate.

The translated text is processed using natural language processing library spaCy and large and small entities from the input text are recognized. Also, the sentimental analysis of the input is generated using another NLP python library named TextBlob. It determines whether the text input is positive, neutral, or negative based on its content.

In the second phase the entities generated using spaCy model are combined and it is again combined with the first two lines of the news paragraph it is processed using google cloud vision API to predict the category of the news. The Entities recognized using spaCy are used as the Tags for the news and category predicted using cloud vision is specified as the category of the news.

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IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Pre-processing

Data pre-processing is a crucial part in preparing raw data for analysis. It involves transforming and cleaning data. It significantly increases the quality of the results. It helps for increasing the accuracy of the model and Efficiency of the results.

- Noise reduction- By cleaning and transforming data, preprocessing removes irrelevant or noisy information.
- Removing Stop words - Remove frequently used terms (stop words) that have little relevance and noise to your analysis.
- Punctuation Removal:

Removing punctuation marks like periods, commas, and quotation marks can help clean the text and reduce noise.

B. Language Detection and Translation:

The system first determines the language of the user's input while creating a news article. This is crucial for ensuring accurate translation and analysis.

The system initiates when users provide news content in their native language. To ensure accurate processing and analysis, a language detection mechanism determines the language of the news article.

C. Translation to English

The Google Translate API is used to convert the user's input into English, standardizing the content and making it language neutral. Consistent analysis across different source languages is made possible by this translation into a common language.

D. NLP Analysis Using spaCy.

The translated text undergoes processing using spaCy, a powerful natural language processing library. SpaCy is employed to identify large entities (such as names, locations, organizations) and small entities (like dates and quantities) within the text. These large entities function as essential keywords and context providers for the news article, enhancing its overall analysis.

```

@app.route('/api/get_entities', methods=['POST'])
def get_entities():
    data = request.get_json() # Get the JSON data from the request
    text = data.get('text', '') # Get the text from the JSON data

    # Process the text using the spaCy models
    doc_lg = nlp_lg(text)
    doc_sm = nlp_sm(text)

    analysis = TextBlob(text)

    # Determine sentiment
    if analysis.sentiment.polarity > 0:
        sentiment = "Positive"
    elif analysis.sentiment.polarity == 0:
        sentiment = "Neutral"
    else:
        sentiment = "Negative"

    entities_lg = [(ent.text, ent.label_) for ent in doc_lg.ents]
    entities_sm = [(ent.text, ent.label_) for ent in doc_sm.ents]

    return jsonify({"entities_lg": entities_lg, "entities_sm": entities_sm, "sentiment": sentiment})
    
```

E. Sentiment Analysis Using TextBlob

To assess the sentiment of the news article, the system employs TextBlob, a Python library designed for text data processing. TextBlob conducts sentiment analysis, classifying the text as positive, neutral, or negative based on its contextual content.

F. Combining Entities and Initial Paragraph

The system collects the large entities recognized by spaCy in the previous step, which serve as vital keywords and tags relevant to the news article's content. These identified entities are combined with the first two lines of the news article to ensure contextual grounding of the analysis.

```

console.log('Entities:', data.entities_sm);
setEntities(data.entities_lg);
setSentiment(data.sentiment);

const CombinedText = data.entities_lg.map((entityText) => entityText).join(' ');

const paragraphs = textConvertedInput.split('\n\n'); // Assuming paragraphs are separated by two newlines
const firstTwoParagraphs = paragraphs.slice(0, 2).join('\n\n');

const combinedContent = `${firstTwoParagraphs}${CombinedText}`;
console.log("This is combined output", combinedContent);

if(combinedContent){
    const Textresponse = await axios.post('http://localhost:8000/checkCategory', {
        combinedContent,
    });
    if(Textresponse.status === 200){
        setcheckCategory(true);
        console.log("Server response showing category", Textresponse.data.categories);
        setcategories(Textresponse.data.categories);
    }
}
    
```

G. Category Prediction Using Google Cloud Vision

The combined content entities and initial paragraph is passed through the Google Cloud Vision API. Although primarily associated with image analysis, Google Cloud Vision is equally capable of text analysis. The system utilizes this API to predict the category of the news article based on the amalgamated content. The category predicted by Google Cloud Vision becomes the official classification for the news article.

H. Text Summarization with Transformers Models:

The input text, which may be a lengthy news article, is processed by the summarization model. The summarizer takes the input and generates a concise summary.

Parameters such as "max_length" and "min_length" are set to control the length of the summary, ensuring it falls within a specific range.

The system generates a summary that is clear, informative,

```

@app.route('/api/get_summary', methods=['POST'])
def get_summary():
    data = request.get_json() # Get the JSON data from the request
    text = data.get('text', '')
    summarizer = pipeline(task="summarization", model="facebook/bart-large-cnn")
    summary = summarizer(text, max_length=200, min_length=150, do_sample=False)
    return jsonify({"summary": summary})
    
```

Figure: Final Output

I. Image Object Detection with DETR Model:

Users submit image URLs via a JSON request, and the system retrieves and processes these images. It employs the DETR (Detection Transformer) model along with a corresponding processor for this task. Through this process, the model identifies objects within the images. These objects are used for searching the existing images that match the objects and to reuse the image for the new article.

And news can be created only if the content is positive or neutral otherwise is it prevented.

In the second phase entities recognized using spaCy are combined with the initial part of the news article which be the basis form for news categorization. Utilizing the Google Cloud Vision API, the system predicts the category of the news article, considering both textual and visual elements. The result is the official classification of the news, simplifying content organization and retrieval. Overall, the system's results include standardized English content, improved entity recognition, sentiment analysis, and efficient news categorization.

This outcome collectively enhances the news analysis making it a powerful tool in the digital news landscape.

IV. CONCLUSION

The project presents a comprehensive and technologically advanced solution for addressing the challenges of news analysis and categorization in the digital age. Leveraging state-of-the-art technologies such as NER using NLP, sentiment analysis, text summarization, and image processing, the system provides users with the ability to input news descriptions in multiple languages. The project overcomes the multilingual content challenges and enhances entity recognition precision.

It offers clear and concise news summaries and efficient object detection from images to increase the user experience. The integration of the Google Cloud Vision API significantly helps automated news categorization, making the system a tool for organizing and accessing news content. This system not only demonstrates the power of AI and NLP in the news content analysis but also the potential applications of these technologies.

The system exemplifies how digital information management is changing and gives an efficient and creative solution for the news analysis and automated categorization in the digital world.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

For future scope for the system include improved fake news detection, personalized news delivery and analysis, real-time event tracking and the ability to analyze the audio content. Data visualization and blockchain technology for presenting and verifying data, Collaborative newsrooms, Ethical AI practices, regional news analysis. These enhancements will collectively help for advanced news analysis and that meets the users demand in the digital era.

VI. REFERENCES

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Figure: Workflow diagram of the proposed system

V. RESULTS

The system results are two-fold and incredibly beneficial for news analysis. It detects the user's language first and convert it into English. The natural language processing library spaCy is used to identify significant entities and crucial keywords are detected. Additionally, TextBlob performs sentiment analysis, for categorizing the content as positive, neutral, or negative.

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